

ASSESSMENT OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A HEALTHCARE SETTING: A PRESCRIPTION AUDIT STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

Prescription auditing serves as a crucial tool in evaluating healthcare quality and optimizing drug usage patterns. This study aimed to assess medication errors across the prescribing, dispensing, and administration stages in a healthcare setting. The World Health Organization's core prescribing indicators were employed to analyse prescribing practices. Major prescribing errors primarily encompassed dosage inaccuracies, abbreviation misuse, and documentation lapses, leading to medication errors. Dispensing errors were comparatively minor, focusing on incorrect drug dispersion and labelling errors. Administration errors, including dose omissions and documentation inaccuracies, were also identified. A total of 350 prescriptions were audited, revealing 151 prescribing errors, 9 dispensing errors, and 24 administration errors. These findings underscore the imperative for robust quality assurance measures and enhanced healthcare provider training to mitigate medication-related risks and enhance patient safety.

Key words: Prescription Audit, Drug utilization research, WHO prescribing indicators, Prescription error, Clinical pharmacist, Health related quality of life.

INTRODUCTION:

The core prescribing indicators of the World Health Organization (WHO) are extremely standardized instruments that are capable of accurately evaluating the key components of drug usage patterns [1]. A Prescription Audit (PA) is defined as “the review and evaluation of health-care procedures and their documentation to compare the quality of care which are being provided, with the accepted set standards” [2,3,4]. The WHO defined the drug utilization research as a marketing, distribution, prescription and use of drugs in society with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social and economic consequences [5,6]. An audit of such prescribing practices helps to improve the drug usage pattern by pointing out the subtleties and important procedures that need to be changed to provide patients with better treatment. [1,3,7] Medication error is “any preventable event that may cause or lead to inappropriate medication use or patient harm, while the medication is in control of the health care professional, patient, or consumer” are prevalent in hospitals and are a major global cause of preventable mortality [8].

Numerous drug errors, including prescription errors, transcription errors, dispensing errors, and administration errors, have been documented in studies conducted worldwide [8].

The reported drug mistake rates in Indian studies range from 7.6% to 44%. [8], Adverse drug events (ADEs) can result in longer hospital stays, a twofold increase in the risk of mortality, and an estimated 7000 fatalities annually in the US alone. Prescription errors are responsible for 0.4–15.4% of US prescriptions issued and 7.4–18.7% of UK prescriptions written.[9], In Australia, an adverse event happened in 16.6% of admissions, leaving 13.7% of patients permanently disabled and 4.9% dead; 51% of bad occurrences were thought to have been avoidable [10].

Roughly 30% of issues that arise during hospital stays are associated with pharmaceutical mistakes. Errors with medications can lead to higher expenses, longer hospital stays, or even potentially fatal consequences. Therefore, it's critical to recognize, categorize, and analyse medication errors and to put the right measures in place to reduce them [11].

The world's third-largest producer of generic medications is India. Patient compliance is increased by making additional drug choices from the National List of Essential Medicines (NLEM), which is based on sufficient data on cost-effectiveness, safety, and efficacy [1,5].

Irrational prescriptions can result in poor care, which puts the patient at risk for increased costs, unwarranted side effects, unneeded mental suffering, and sickness extension or worsening. The WHO develops a set of "core prescribing indicators" with the goal of enhancing patient practices that involve rational drug use. [2,4]

The quality of prescribed medical care, including techniques utilized for diagnosis and treatment, the appropriate use of various resources, and the impact on patients' quality of life, is systematically and critically analysed in a PA. It is a continuous process that looks for ways to raise the standard of medical care. [2,7]

The prescription indicators are primarily used to evaluate how well medical practitioners perform in terms of prescribing medications appropriately. [12,13], Because PA offers documentary evidence, it can be used to assess the quality of medical care provided.[2] Medications are essential to the provision of healthcare services worldwide. The right use of medications can significantly lower morbidity and mortality rates worldwide.[12]

In an ideal prescription, the patient's full name, age, address, hospital registration number, date of prescription, clinical diagnosis, and the generic name of the medication being used, along with its dosage, frequency of administration, and total quantity to be supplied for the course of treatment, should all be clearly specified. The prescribing physician's signature, along with the patient's name, medical registration number, and, if available, address, should be completed. [2,4,14]

Nonetheless, according to data from the WHO, almost 50% of medications are sold, distributed, or prescribed improperly. [12,15] Prescription errors are prevalent and can impact anywhere from 4.2 to 82% of prescriptions, according to newly available data. Such mistakes may lead to unfavourable outcomes, risky medical interventions, increased treatment expenses, ineffective resource usage, and illogical medication use. Approximately 4 out of every 1000 prescriptions contain mistakes that could have negative consequences. Research has indicated that 56% of these avoidable adverse occurrences happened during the medication ordering process. Both systemic and individual variables can lead to prescription errors. The first vital step in creating safer systems and averting unfavourable occurrences is detecting such faults. [4,15]

Given that between 25 and 70 percent of global healthcare spending is allocated to medications, this could have an impact on spending on healthcare budgets. Therefore, it is believed that changing how people utilize medications will help to maximize the use of the little resources available to the medical field while simultaneously raising the standard of care provided to patients [12]. Employee training on a regular basis, large-scale gatherings, internal audits, and group meetings should all increase the compliance rate. [3]

The key goal of maintaining the quality of healthcare services in both the public and commercial sectors is the prudent use of medications. [3,16] The WHO defines rational drug use as: "Patients receive medications appropriate to their clinical needs, at the lowest possible cost to them and their community, for an adequate period of time, in doses that meet individual physiological and pharmacological requirements" [3,17].

Effects of drug usage that is not reasonable can be observed in a variety of ways: A decline in medication therapy quality that raises morbidity and death, Resource waste that raises prices and decreases the availability of other essential medications, A higher

chance of unfavourable outcomes, like medication resistance developing and unpleasant drug responses, Psychosocial effects: Patients may see a perceived rise in the demand for pharmaceuticals if they start to believe that there is "a pill for every ill." [14]

Anti Microbial Stewardship (AMS) refers to “coordinated interventions designed to improve and measure the appropriate use of antimicrobial agents by promoting the selection of the optimal antimicrobial drug regimen, dose, duration of therapy and route of administration” [18]

Antibiotics will be essential in reducing morbidity and death rates in emerging nations with higher rates of infectious disease. Antibiotic resistance is a global issue that poses a concern. Pneumonia is the leading cause of death for children in India, accounting for an estimated 410,000 fatalities annually as a measure of disease burden [14].

The following are possible advantages of prescription audits:

- Raising the bar for quality and professionalism, encourage staff growth and training, provide financial and human resources for improved assurance and patient care, Determine and get rid of subpar or inexperienced procedures, Gain proficiency in presenting pertinent results. [3,13,19]

The Prescription Quality Index (PQI), which was created by Hassan et al. in 2010, is a tool used to assess how well drugs are prescribed for chronic illnesses. In the form of questions, it has 22 criteria. The PQI has been hailed as the perfect instrument, adaptable to a wide range of drugs and clinical situations, and simple to use in a variety of contexts with sparse data availability.[19]

The average number of medications prescribed per prescription aids in the researcher's investigation of polypharmacy in the prescription and aids in the prediction of potential ADRs. [5,20]

The participation of clinical pharmacists and pharmacologists in prescription audits can yield important insights into the hospital's overall documentation process. These insights can aid in identifying the cause of incomplete admission patient prescription files and in raising the standard of outpatient and patient department documentation.[21]

Clinical pharmacists have gradually begun to be incorporated into private hospital environments in India; however, their responsibilities are still restricted to medication reconciliation, drug interaction detection and prevention, identification and reporting of adverse drug reactions, and support for doctors and surgeons during ward rounds. [18]

The rise in this certification rate led to a strong push for Clinical Pharmacists (CPs) to be included in healthcare teams as vital healthcare providers in order to promote evidence-based medicine and logical therapy. The pharmacy practice department's provision of pharmaceutical treatment is essential to enhancing the overall Sah, et al.: Clinical Audit at a NABH Accredited Hospital 118 Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice, Vol. 12, Issue 2,

April–June 2019, provide hospitals with income while ensuring the provision of high-quality care.[17]

A research that emphasizes patient care, condenses important ideas, and presents a workable plan for creating, putting into practice, assessing, and maintaining an interdisciplinary quality improvement system is required. [22] A complex concept, health-related quality of life (HRQoL) encompasses aspects linked to social, mental, emotional, and physical functioning. [15,20]

Misuse, abuse, and underuse of medications are examples of poor prescribing practices that can result in risky treatment, health risks, financial strain on patients, and resource waste. Errors in prescription writing encourage drug abuse and lower patient compliance. These behaviours also raise patient mortality, morbidity, and cost burden by fostering the development of drug interactions, drug resistance, and adverse drug reactions. [6]

According to the current review, in order to encourage rational prescribing, physicians should participate in extensive training programs, educational initiatives, or prescribing awareness campaigns regarding the WHO prescribing indicators. This intervention in healthcare settings may also help to alleviate the problem of overprescribing or irrational drug prescription.[23] Prescription audits and feedback combined are recognized to be an effective method for raising the standard of prescribing.[24] The degree to which practitioners prescribe from the national essential medicine list is also gauged by WHO measures.[25]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We have selected total more than 350 prescription from inpatients department of all wards of the hospital and we audited different parameters based on prescribing, dispensing and administrating.

Prescribing parameters:

1. No/Wrong Dose
2. No/Wrong Unit
3. No/Wrong Frequency
4. No/Wrong Route
5. No/Wrong Concentration/Dilution
6. No/Wrong Rate of Administration
7. Drug Allergies not documented
8. Non-usage of Capital letters for drug names
9. Illegible Handwriting
10. Error Prone Abbreviation used
11. Non-modification of drug dose keeping in mind drug-drug and food-drug Interaction
12. Presence of Therapeutic Duplication

Dispensing parameters:

1. Wrong Drug Dispensed
2. Wrong dose dispensed
3. Wrong formulation dispensed
4. Expired/Near-expiry drug dispensed
5. No/wrong labelling
6. Delay in dispense
7. Generic or class substitute done without consultation with the prescribing doctors

Administrating parameters:

1. Wrong patient
2. Dose omission
3. Improper dose
4. Wrong drug
5. Wrong dosage form
6. Wrong route of administration
7. Wrong route
8. Wrong duration

9. Wrong time
10. No documentation of drug administration

Collected data were observed and analysed using Microsoft excel office, analysed data are presented in table and graphs.

RESULTS:

We audited more than 1000 drugs in 350 prescriptions in which we evaluate different parameters related to the prescribing, Dispensing and Administrating. We compare prescription audit parameters with WHO standards based on WHO core prescribing indicators and we analysed total 184 errors including prescription, Dispensing and Administration. In which prescribing error were 151, Dispensing errors were 09 and Administrating errors were 24. Ration of prescription error, Dispensing error and Administration error was 82%, 4.9% and 13% respectively.

Analysis of Prescribing audit criteria:

As shown in table we found major prescribing errors were in writing dose, their units, concentration/dilution of some parenteral medications and using of some abbreviation which leading to the medication error, other than this we found errors in writing in frequency of drug, route of drug, not usage of capital letters in drug name, found some interactions between drugs, presence of therapeutic duplication in one prescription, and documentation of allergy status of patient in prescription. Total 151 prescribing errors audited from 350

PRESCRIPTION			
Sr No.	Audit Criteria	Total prescription audited	No. of errors
1	No/Wrong Dose	350	56
2	No/Wrong Unit	350	33
3	No/Wrong Frequency	350	01
4	No/Wrong Route	350	03
5	No/Wrong Concentration/Dilution	350	15
6	No/Wrong Rate of Administration	350	00
7	Drug Allergies not documented	350	09
8	Non-usage of Capital letters for drug names	350	08
9	Illegible Handwriting	350	05
10	Error Prone Abbreviation used	350	16
11	Non-modification of drug dose keeping in mind drug-drug and food-drug Interaction	350	03
12	Presence of Therapeutic Duplication	350	02

prescriptions.

Analysis of Dispensing audit criteria:

DISPENSING			
Sr No.	Audit Criteria	Total prescription audited	No. of errors
1	Wrong Drug Dispensed	350	03
2	Wrong Dose Dispensed	350	03
3	Wrong Formulation Dispensed	350	00
4	Expired/Near-expiry Drug Dispensed	350	01
5	No/Wrong Labelling	350	02
6	Delay in Dispense	350	00
7	Generic or class substitute done without consultation with the prescribing doctor	350	00

As shown in table we found minor errors in dispensing of drug than the prescribing and administrating errors, we analysed dispensing errors in following criteria: wrong drug dispensed, wrong dose dispensed, labelling not done in dispensed medication and expired or near expired drug dispensed audited total 09 dispensing errors from 350 prescriptions.

Analysis of Administration audit criteria:

ADMINISTRATION			
Sr No.	Audit Criteria	Total prescription audited	No. of errors
1	Wrong Patient	350	00
2	Dose Omission	350	05
3	Improper Dose	350	07
4	Wrong Drug	350	04
5	Wrong Dosage Form	350	03
6	Wrong Route of administration	350	00
7	Wrong Rate	350	01
8	Wrong Duration	350	00
9	Wrong Time	350	02
10	No Documentation of Drug Administration	350	02

As shown in table we found minor errors in administration of drug in following criteria: dose omission, improper dose of drug, wrong drug administered either wrong dose or wrong combination or wrong formulation, administered drug with wrong rate or at wrong time duration and also includes some documentation errors by nursing staff. We found total 24 administrating errors from 350 prescriptions.

Discussion:

The study identified significant prescribing errors, particularly in dosage, units, and medication concentration, highlighting the need for improved clarity and precision in prescription writing. Predominantly, prescribing errors emerged as a significant concern, with 151 instances identified among 350 prescriptions. These errors encompassed various aspects, including dosage inaccuracies, unit discrepancies, and issues with medication concentration and dilution. Additionally, the use of ambiguous abbreviations contributed to the potential for medication errors. Dispensing errors, though fewer in number (9 errors), highlighted the importance of vigilant oversight during the dispensing process, particularly in verifying the correct drug, dose, and labelling. Furthermore, administration errors, totalling 24 instances, emphasized the need for meticulous attention to detail by nursing staff. These errors ranged from dose omissions to incorrect drug administration, underlining the critical role of healthcare professionals in ensuring safe medication practices. Notably, documentation errors were also observed among the administration errors, underscoring the importance of accurate record-keeping in patient care. Overall, the study findings underscore the multifaceted nature of medication errors and the imperative for comprehensive strategies to mitigate risks across all stages of the medication use process. Addressing prescribing errors requires enhanced clarity and precision in prescription writing practices, alongside measures to minimize abbreviations and improve drug interaction awareness. In the dispensing phase, robust checking procedures and adherence to labelling protocols are essential to prevent errors. Additionally, healthcare providers must prioritize thorough training and ongoing education to promote adherence to proper administration techniques and documentation practices. By addressing these findings comprehensively, healthcare systems can enhance medication safety and improve patient outcomes.

Conclusion:

The study highlights the pervasive nature of medication errors across the prescribing, dispensing, and administration stages, emphasizing the critical need for proactive interventions to enhance patient safety. The high prevalence of prescribing errors, including dosage inaccuracies and abbreviation misuse, underscores the importance of standardized prescription practices and increased awareness among healthcare providers. Similarly, while dispensing errors were fewer in number, they underscore the significance of rigorous verification processes to prevent incorrect drug dispensation. Furthermore, administration errors, coupled with documentation inaccuracies, underscore the essential role of vigilant nursing oversight and meticulous record-keeping in minimizing medication-related risks. Addressing these findings requires a multifaceted approach encompassing improved prescription clarity, enhanced dispensing protocols, and comprehensive staff training on safe medication practices. By implementing robust quality assurance measures and fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement, healthcare systems can mitigate medication errors, safeguard patient well-being, and ultimately enhance the overall quality of care delivery.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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